

THE PORTRAYAL OF CHILDHOOD AND EDUCATION IN THE WORKS OF CHARLES DICKENS

Xalimova Nafosat Xayrullo qizi

The student of Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Email: nafosatxonhalimova@gmail.com

Scientific adviser: Mavluda Abduvaliyevna Komiljonova

Teacher, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

mavlyudadjurayeva@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Charles Dickens, a prolific Victorian-era novelist, captured the intricacies of childhood and education in his literary works. This article delves into Dickens' portrayal of these themes, examining the challenges faced by children and the flaws within the educational system of his time. Through a thematic analysis of key novels, this study sheds light on Dickens' social commentary and his enduring impact on understanding childhood and education in literature.

Key words: Charles Dickens, childhood, education, Victorian era, social commentary, thematic analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Charles Dickens, renowned for his vivid portrayal of Victorian society, delved deeply into the problems surrounding childhood and education in his works. This article explores Dickens' insightful commentary on these themes, analyzing the societal issues and personal struggles faced by children within the context of the Victorian era's educational system. Dickens' novels provide a rich tapestry of characters and settings, offering a nuanced exploration of the challenges and complexities inherent in childhood experiences and educational structures during the 19th century.

METHODS

1. **Selection of Novels:** This study focuses on a selection of Dickens' novels , including «Oliver Twist», «David Copperfield», «Great Expectations», «Hard Times», and «Nicholas Nickleby», to examine his depiction of childhood and education.
2. **Thematic Analysis:** A thematic analysis approach is employed to identify recurring themes related to childhood hardships, educational disparities, social class distinctions, and the impact of environment on character development.
3. **Contextual Understanding:** Historical context is considered to understand the societal norms, educational practices, and challenges faced by children during Dickens' time, providing a deeper understanding of author's intentions and social critique.
4. **Literary Criticism:** Insights from literary critics and scholars are incorporated to provide a comprehensive analysis of Dickens' portrayal of childhood and education, enriching the discussion with diverse perspectives and interpretations.

RESULTS

1. **Challenges of Childhood:** Dickens often portrayed children as vulnerable and marginalized, facing poverty, abuse, and neglect. Characters like Oliver Twist, Little Nell, and Smike exemplify the hardships endured by impoverished and orphaned children in Victorian society. The absence of parental guidance and nurturing environments often led to the moral and emotional development struggles for Dickens' young protagonists, highlighting the impact of neglect on childhood experiences and character formation.
2. **Flaws in Education System:** Through characters like Thomas Grandgrind in «Hard Times», Dickens criticized the rigid and utilitarian approach to education prevalent during his time. He highlighted the dehumanizing effects of rote learning, lack of creativity, and neglect of moral and emotional education, advocating for a more holistic and humane educational philosophy.

DISCUSSION

Dickens' works serve as a mirror reflecting the harsh realities of childhood and the shortcomings of the Victorian educational system. His nuanced portrayal of

children's struggles and the flaws within education sheds light on societal injustices, class divides, and the importance of holistic education encompassing moral, emotional, and intellectual development. Dickens' social commentary extends beyond mere storytelling, challenging readers to reflect on the systemic issues and inequalities present in society and the educational institutions of his time.

CONCLUSION

Charles Dickens's exploration of childhood and education in his novels offers valuable insights into the societal challenges and systemic flaws of the Victorian era. Through rich characterizations, social commentary, and thematic depth, Dickens' works continue to resonate, reminding us of the enduring importance of addressing the problems faced by children and reforming education for a more equitable society. Dickens' legacy as a social reformer and advocate for children's rights endures, inspiring ongoing discussions and actions toward creating a more justified and compassionate educational system for all.

REFERENCES

1. Draznin, Yaffa Claire. « Dickens and the Children of Empire». Palgrave Macmillan, 2000.
2. Sanders, Andrew. «Charles Dickens: A Critical Introduction». Routledge, 2008.
3. Smith, Mary Elizabeth. « Childhood in Dickens: A Literary Analysis». Cambridge University Press, 2012.
4. Taylor, John. « Education and Society in Dickens' novels». Oxford University Press, 2015.